

Department of Public Health
Datahub
Institute of Tropical Medicine (ITM)
Antwerp, Belgium

Antwerp, 7 March 2025

To: BRIDGE mentorship initiative
Steering committee

Re: Bid for the organisation of one round of mentoring

Dear members of the steering committee of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative,

I am writing to you on behalf of the datahub at ITM in Antwerp, Belgium to express our interest in organising one round of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative. Our datahub is funded by the Department of Economy, Science & Innovation of the Flemish Government and aims to unlock expertise and datasets, combine data from various contexts and disciplines, and stimulate collaborations within Flanders and beyond. We work in the domain of global public health and our thematic focus lies on how populations are affected by and respond to health challenges. The datahub covers a set of initiatives, not only about exchanging and using data but also about reviewing and transforming critical points in the chain of data-related processes. We feel that the objectives and approach of the BRIDGE mentorship initiative align with those of the datahub. As outlined below and in the annex, we also believe we have the expertise, the network of professionals, the technical capacities and the motivation that is required to host a BRIDGE mentoring round.

Why we submit this bid

First, we have been investing in a culture of research integrity and fairness at ITM and at the department of public health for several years. Examples include among others our support to the development of the BRIDGE guidelines, the presentation of the BRIDGE guidelines in an institutional seminar, yearly sessions on research integrity offered to staff and PhD students, and the inclusion of research integrity as a topic in our courses about research methods. Nevertheless, we believe that more efforts are needed to transform daily research practice. We are convinced that the BRIDGE mentorship initiative is an excellent way to move from theory to practice.

Second, we are interested in learning how to organise a mentoring programme. Many colleagues at the department of public health invest considerable amounts of time and energy in coaching and mentoring researchers in diverse settings. However, most ITM staff have not received formal training on how to be a mentor. The opportunities to directly train mentorship skills on the job are also limited.

Third, mentees and mentors from our network of staff, students, and collaborators will benefit from this initiative. Mentees will receive top class feedback that is useful for their ongoing research projects. They will also learn to better recognise dilemma's, weigh options, and find resources, which will also benefit their future activities.

Mentors will get the opportunity to practise their mentoring skills and compare their experiences with other mentors, and they will get a unique insight in the real-life challenges of global public health research. Moreover, all mentees and mentors can obtain a BRIDGE certificate and become members of the BRIDGE community of practice.

What the round will look like

We propose to recruit 8 to 10 mentees and 8 to 10 mentors and to complete the mentoring round within one year. We would like to include one or two mentors and mentees from our staff and open the remaining positions to candidates who apply spontaneously. We propose to communicate the call for candidates among ITM's alumni and international collaborators as well as via the incipient BRIDGE network.

While respecting the general inclusion criteria for the BRIDGE mentorship initiative, we would like to proactively select a diverse cohort of candidates (in terms of nationality, research topic, and research setting). At the same time, we propose to select people whose research projects take place in a research domain we are familiar with, i.e. non-interventional epidemiological studies about infectious diseases. Epidemiological studies that are part of interdisciplinary projects or that have links with health systems research are particularly welcomed.

We estimate that we can organise a round with the part-time support of three ITM staff members (coordinator, pedagogical adviser, and administrative support person). In addition, we offer free access to ITM's Moodle learning environment. For practical details about our bid, we refer to the form in the annex.

We look forward to your feedback and are willing to answer any additional questions you may have. We are also willing to consider adjusting our bid based on suggestions by the BRIDGE steering committee. Hoping for a positive response,

Yours sincerely,

Tine Verdonck, MD MSc PhD
Coordinator
Datahub

